

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF AUDIO-VIDEO PRESENTATION TO IMPROVE READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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Development and Utilization of Audio-Video Presentation to Improve Reading Comprehension Skills

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the contribution of developing and utilizing audio-video presentations to improve the reading comprehension skills of the struggling readers at Juan B. Tabla Elementary School, South I District, Iligan City Division, in the school year 2023-2024. The study determined the pretest and posttest scores of the learners before and after using the intervention. In addition, it also answered if there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in the three dimensions of reading comprehension after using the audio-video presentations. The study utilized a quasi-experimental design. It involved 48 learners as participants. A standardized instrument from Phil-IRI intended for sixth-grade learners was used in gathering the data. These selections were made into audio-video presentations that were used in this study. The study revealed that there was a significant difference between the learners' pretest and posttest scores in the reading dimensions after the integration of the audio-visual presentations. Out of 48 participants, 100% belonged to the frustration level before the intervention. After the intervention, more than half of the total number of participants became instructional readers, which was 58.3%, and 31.3% became independent readers. It showed that there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in the three dimensions of reading comprehension after using audio-video presentations.

Keywords: *development, utilization, reading comprehension skills, audio-video presentations, reading dimensions*

Introduction

One of the lifelong skills that a child must acquire is reading. A child can learn new things, acquire new information, and discover new opportunities for self-improvement through reading. Unfortunately, a large number of Filipino children are categorized as non-readers and frustrated readers. There has been a crisis in education in the Philippines since before the COVID-19 pandemic but has been made worse by it. As stated in the UNICEF 2020 report, less than 15% of Filipino school children, or roughly 3 out of every 20, cannot read simple texts. This is largely because the country's schools have been closed for the longest period of time—more than 70 weeks as of the middle of February 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2019, the World Bank reported that the learning poverty in the country was 69.5% which drastically increased by 30.4% or 90.9% in its recent report in June 2022 during the pandemic (de Vera, 2022).

At Juan B. Tabla Elementary School, it is one of the problems for which we are looking for a solution. Based on the pretest results of the SY 2022-2023 Phil-IRI, 45.03% of learners fell into the frustrated level in both oral and silent reading, where out of 302 learners in grades four to six, 136 were considered as frustrated level readers; 123 were instructional readers; and the remaining were independent readers. These indicate that they cannot read and are unable to understand what they are reading. This scenario is apparent not only in our school but also in most public schools in the Philippines. This was evident in the 2018 study by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). The country ranked last in reading comprehension among the seventy-nine participating countries (Department of Education, 2019); and in Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) in 2019, where the country's result was among the bottom half amid the six ASEAN countries covered for reading, mathematics, and writing literacy (UNICEF Philippines, 2021).

To address this widespread problem in education, educational institutions perceive the potential of utilizing technologies to raise educational standards, beginning with improving reading comprehension levels. Consequently, as a result, they are continuously looking for the ideal technological solutions that can fulfill this promise. One of which is the use of audio-video presentations.

According to Bautista et al. (2018), one of the tools used in modern classrooms is the Smart-TV, making it an emerging tool trend in technology and education. It can play videos, audio recordings, and images that are interactive and encourage pupils to participate more. They also underlined how these kinds of activities make the classes alive and energetic. In addition, Gonzales (2020) stated that video presentations can not only arouse the students' enthusiasm, and keep longer attention, but also widen their horizons, deepen their impressions, and inspire their imaginations. There is growing anticipation that multimedia will improve students' learning experiences (Benbunan-Fich, 2002; Gonzales, 2020) and facilitate interactive instruction, which will motivate students to take greater ownership of their education (Alavi & Leidner, 2002; Gonzales 2020).

The research aimed to give data regarding the effectiveness of audio-visual presentations in enhancing the reading comprehension abilities of struggling readers at Juan B. Tabla Elementary School.

Furthermore, the purpose of this study was to address the challenge put out by the Department of Education in DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019, "Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs)". This reading proficiency campaign has a mission to consistently generate law-abiding, responsible individuals who possess the fundamental knowledge and abilities needed for lifelong study. Additionally, it states that all students must become proficient readers in their grade level and that teachers must work with students to help them

improve their reading abilities.

Since this study focused on audio-video presentations, it anchored on the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines, under Section 10, Art. XIV, where science and technology are deemed essential for the nation's development and progress. The 1987 constitution makes clear that the state places a high priority on invention, innovation, and research and development as well as their application. It also highlights the importance of science and technology education, training, and services for delivering high-quality education. Moreover, Republic Act 9155 stated that one of the school administrator's duties is to see to it that new and creative forms of education are used to improve learning outcomes. Hence, this study would contribute to addressing the need for teachers to adapt to how they instruct the current generation to improve the standard of education. The study was conducted in the first quarter of the school year 2023-2024.

The researcher has been a public school teacher for five years. She also serves on her school's reading committee and has received a Smart TV to use for delivering audio-visual presentations. In the school where the study was performed, the researcher hopes to shed some light on the contribution of utilizing audio-video presentations as an intervention to enhance the reading skills of struggling readers.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine how using audio-video presentations helped the frustration-level readers at Juan B. Tabla Elementary School, South I District, Iligan City Division, enhance their reading comprehension skills in the school year 2023–2024. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the pretest scores of the learners before using audio-video presentations?
2. What are the scores of the learners in the pretest and posttest in terms of literal, inferential, and critical comprehension?
3. What are the posttest scores of the learners after using audio-video presentations?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in the three dimensions of reading comprehension after using the audio-video presentations?
5. What output can be designed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods used in the study. It also discussed the research design, research environment, respondents and sampling procedure, research instruments and its validity, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

This study used quasi-experimental research design. The pretest and posttest for the one-group technique was conducted. In this approach, a pretest was given to the sixth-grade learners to identify their reading levels. Learners who belonged to the frustration levels were subjected to this study. These learners were exposed to audio-video presentations that aimed at enhancing their reading comprehension skills. A posttest with similar contents to the pretest was administered to see if there is a difference in the scores before and after using the audio-video presentations.

Participants

The participants to this study were the grade six learners at Juan B. Tabla Elementary School enrolled for the school year 2023–2024. Purposive and cluster sampling were used to identify the participants to this study. They took the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pretest to identify their reading level. Only the learners who fell into the frustrated category were included in the experiment which was 48 or 47.52% of the total population. It used purposeful sampling because the learners classified as frustration-level readers were the only ones subjected to this study. Since learners who shared the same level of frustration were selected as research participants, this study likewise employed the cluster method of sampling.

The table below shows the number of learners who belonged to the frustration level per section.

Table 1. Distribution of Learner-Participants

<i>Section</i>	<i>Total Number of Learners</i>	<i>Total Number of Learner-Participants</i>	
		<i>Frustration Level</i>	
Santan	35	10	
Rosal	34	15	
Cattleya	32	23	
Total	101	48	

Instruments

This study utilized a standardized instrument from Phil-IRI intended for grade six learners. The said test covers the dimensions of reading comprehension namely: literal, inferential, and critical. There were three selections namely: Chameleons, The Philippine Eagle,

and Home to Millions of Fish. The selections were a total of twenty (20) items.

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory or Phil-IRI is a non-formal reading inventory made up of graded passages intended to assess each learner's proficiency in reading. These three types of assessments aim to find the learner's independent, instructional, and frustration levels. Their reading levels were determined by dividing their scores by the total number of items and multiplying the result by 100. Those who scored between 80% and 100% were considered independent readers; those who scored between 61% and 79% were considered instructional readers, and those who scored 60% or below were considered frustrated readers. These standards or guidelines for scoring were derived from the Phil-IRI.

The pretest was conducted to assess the reading level of the learners in terms of their comprehension. Those learners who belonged to the frustration level were chosen as participants of this study and were subjected to an intervention using audio-video presentations.

Selections were made into audio-video presentations. The videos used in this study were produced by a video maker, whom the researcher employed and worked with. The researcher chose the selections to be made into videos and added the audio and subtitles after making sure that they were synchronized with the visuals presented. She then reviewed the videos and made the necessary improvements. These materials were verified by the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) coordinators in the district where the school belonged to ensure that they were suitable to the level of the participants. The audio-video materials were assessed using the Expert Validation Sheet (EVS) for non-print materials adopted from the Department of Education Learning Resource Management and Development System or DepEd LRMDs. Four factors were taken into consideration when evaluating comments and suggestions regarding the acceptability and relevance of the audio-video presentations: (1) content quality; (2) instructional quality; (3) technical quality; and (4) mechanics.

Lesson plans were developed by the researcher in this study to practice the comprehension skills of the participants. A posttest was administered to measure the participants' progress after the intervention.

Procedure

A series of steps were administered by the researcher before the gathering of data. A letter was made subject for approval by the Iligan City Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal where this study was conducted to allow her to gather the data necessary for the study. First, to be able to produce valid results, the researcher administered a pretest to all grade six learners to identify their reading level using standardized reading materials in Phil-IRI for Grade 6 in accordance with DepEd Order 14, s. 2018. Those who fell into the frustrated category were the participants of this study.

Every three times each week, during the scheduled "learning recovery continuity program," learners were grouped based on their reading level using the pull-out scheme, where all the frustration-level readers were grouped into one classroom and the researcher was the one who administered the class. Verified audio-video presentations were utilized as a learning or instructional tool for reading to test their contribution to the learners' reading comprehension skills. In addition to the audio-video presentations provided in this research, participants were additionally exposed to other audio-video materials to be utilized within a quarter. The researcher recorded the scores using Microsoft Excel to monitor the improvement of each participant.

Then, after one grading period of applying this approach, a post-test was given to evaluate the contribution of the audio-video presentation on enhancing the participants' reading comprehension skills. The results were collated and submitted to the accredited statistician.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the data which were gathered from the study:

For Problems 1, 2, and 3, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were utilized to determine the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents.

For Problem 3, a Paired T-Test was used to determine the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data were the main topics of this section. It included the information acquired, the outcomes of the statistical analysis, and the conclusions' interpretation. These are shown in tables according to the order of the particular research problem about the use of audio-video presentations to enhance the study participants' reading comprehension abilities.

Problem 1: What are the pretest scores of the learners before using audio-video presentation?

Table 2 (Figure 1) presents the pretest scores of the learners before using an audio-video presentation. Out of 101 learners, 48 belonged to the frustration level and were subjects of this study. As shown in the table, all belonged to the frustration level which was 100% of the total number of participants. It was clear from the data that the participants were unable to comprehend what they were reading. They encountered difficulties when attempting to comprehend what was being read using the three dimensions of reading comprehension. Even the words used in the composition or statement were beyond their literal comprehension.

Table 2. Pretest Scores (Overall Measure)

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
16 – 20	0	0	Independent
13 – 15	0	0	Instructional
12 and below	48	100.0	Frustration
Total	48	100.0	

Figure 1. Pretest Scores

According to Gonzales (2020), difficulties with reading comprehension were influenced by several factors, including the text, the reader, and the context. She expressed concern about the difficulties with lower – and higher–level reading skills, such as poor vocabulary understanding and problems with syntax processing. Learners who lack fluency were inefficient at decoding the text and were not capable of making connections between what they read and what they already knew. More so, children with limited vocabulary struggled with comprehension for obvious reasons. They were unable to analyze thoroughly on what they had read because they were unable to understand the meaning of the words, which was a fundamental ability for understanding what they were reading.

This suggested that readers were less likely to synthesize, assess, and consider the significance of what they were reading if they struggled with basic comprehension skills, such as the literal dimension. In addition to not taking the content of the text literally, learners also struggled to decipher and connect the meanings of the words they read. This suggested that because they had not yet honed the literal dimension, they had not yet mastered the process of obtaining and connecting the meanings of the text. Furthermore, the outcome indicated that the respondents could not assess, analyze, and pronounce upon the selection they read. This indicated that they were incapable of critical thought. Critical thinking abilities, according to Hart (2019), aided readers in developing their comprehension abilities and creating a satisfying reading experience.

Problem 2: What are the scores of the learners in the pretest and posttest in terms of literal, inferential, and critical comprehension?

Table 3. Literal Scores

Score Range	Pretest		Posttest		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
0 – 1	13	27.1	0	0.0	Frustration
2 – 3	27	56.2	30	62.5	Instructional
4	8	16.7	18	37.5	Independent
Total	48	100.0	48	100.0	

Table 3 shows the pretest and posttest scores of the participants before and after using the audio-video presentations in literal comprehension. As the table shows, during the pretest, 13 or 27.1% belonged to the frustration level, 27 or 56.2% to the instructional level, and only 8 or 16.7% out of the 48 participants belonged to the independent level. This meant that only a few of the participants were proficient in understanding the literal meaning of the words in the selections.

From the results, it could be noted that participants had not yet mastered the lowest level of comprehension, which affected their understanding of how words related to other words in the texts. As cited by Heart (2019), learners relied on their background knowledge to connect what they already knew to the text they were reading. It included both the reader’s real-world experiences and literary knowledge that helped learners become active readers, thus improving their reading comprehension.

On the other hand, using audio-video presentations improved the participants' literal comprehension. More than half of the participants (30 or 62.5%) were now categorized as instructional readers, and the remaining of them (18 or 37.5%) were independent readers. This

only proved that using audio-video materials as a learning tool could improve the reading comprehension of the learners. This was supported by Mercado (2022), who believed that using multimedia presentations could improve the learners' vocabulary, which included not just text and photographs but also other interesting content such as animation and dub voice that could help learners to better understand the ideas.

Table 4. *Inferential Scores*

Score Range	Pretest		Posttest		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
0 - 3	31	64.6	0	0.0	Frustration
4 - 6	16	33.3	11	22.9	Instructional
7 - 10	1	2.1	37	77.1	Independent
Total	48	100.0	48	100.0	

Table 4 presents the pretest and posttest scores of the participants in inferential comprehension. As the table shows, during the pretest, the majority (31 or 64.6%) of the participants were categorized as having a frustration level; 16, or 33.3% were instructional readers, and only 1, or 2.1% belonged to the independent level. This only showed that most of the participants could not understand the underlying meaning of the text. This meant that they had difficulty understanding the concepts and ideas presented in the reading materials. Also, they had not mastered the literal understanding of written symbols through decoding to proceed in making inferences.

On the contrary, after using audio-video presentations, participants became instructional (11 or 22.9%) and independent readers (37 or 77.1%) in inferential comprehension. These results illustrated that participants learned how to interpret and synthesize selections using multimedia presentations. It became easier for the participants to draw on their prior knowledge of a topic and identify relevant text clues to make inferences. According to Munene and Mutsotso (2019), audiovisual teaching aids in the learning process. The teaching-learning process could be aided by videos that piqued viewers' interest in a subject, making it easier to grasp the concepts (Daite et al., 2019). It supported the sensory stimulation theory, which stated that learning was most effective when the senses are activated.

Table 5. *Critical Scores*

Score Range	Pretest		Posttest		Description
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
0 - 2	17	35.4	1	2.1	Frustration
3 - 4	27	56.3	27	56.2	Instructional
5 - 6	4	8.3	20	41.7	Independent
Total	48	100.0	48	100.0	

Table 5 displays the pretest and posttest scores of the participants in critical comprehension. During the pretest, 17 or 35.4% of the participants were categorized as frustration level; 27 or 56.3% were instructional readers, and only 4 or 8.3% belonged to the independent level. This indicated that only a small number of participants could evaluate, analyze, and made judgement to the content of the reading materials they read.

In contrast, the posttest scores of the participants after using audio-video presentations, had improved. Twenty-seven (27) or 56.2% of participants belonged to the instructional level; 20 or 41.7% were independent readers; and only 1 or 2.1% belonged to the frustration level. This showed that audio-video presentations had contributed to the reading comprehension skill of the participants in terms of the critical dimension. Participants were able to distinguish the literal meaning of words from the suggestions or intentions expressed in the selections. Most of them were able to separate important from unimportant information. These distinguished between facts and opinions and determined the writer's purpose and tone. This supported the idea that the success of the learners' learning in today's generation was greatly influenced by the utilization of learning media. Also, it involved using a variety of senses both spoken and nonverbal messages to improve educational standards (Pangestuti & Wati, 2022).

Problem 3: What are the posttest scores of the learners after using audio-video presentation?

Table 6. *Posttest Scores (Overall Measure)*

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
16 - 20	15	31.3	Independent
13 - 15	28	58.3	Instructional
12 and below	5	10.4	Frustration
Total	48	100.0	

Table 6 (Figure 2) displays the posttest scores of the learners after using audio-video presentation. As shown in the table, more than half of the respondents belonged to the instructional level which was 28 or 58.3% of the total respondents and 15 or 31.3% became independent readers. From the frustration level, the majority of them move up to the instructional and independent level. This concluded that after utilizing the audio-video presentation as a teaching tool to improve reading comprehension skills, it had been proven that it contributed to improving their reading comprehension. This indicated that utilizing audio-video presentations could contribute to improving the reading comprehension of the learners. This indicated that the respondents understood the meaning of the words as they were used. The respondents also developed their understanding of how to interpret, synthesize, and put meaning to the literal text and

were somewhat able to think critically after they utilized the audio-video presentations.

Figure 2. Posttest Scores

According to data cited by Laird in support of his theory, adults possessed the majority of our knowledge, with 75% of it being acquired through observation. Then, touch, smell, and taste, which were used 12% of the time, came in second, followed by hearing, which was used 13% of the time. Learning could be enhanced by stimulating the senses, particularly the visual sense. The learners were given a sensory learning experience that was more engaging, simpler to remember, and easier to recall through the use of pictures, color, music, and other strategies. Mercado (2022) supported to this idea, saying that in order to teach students who were 21st-century learners, teachers must employ multimedia presentations. To ensure that the topic was fully understood when teaching the current generation, these materials should contain more engaging content than only text and images, such as animations and dub voice. In addition, he emphasized that using videos adapts to the many learning styles of children by providing a special blend of sound, action, and emotion that could help children better grasp their surroundings.

Marshall (2001) provided a quotation that Putri et al. (2021) cited, indicating that people tended to remember 10% of what they read, 20% of what they heard, 30% of what they saw, and 50% of both what they heard and saw.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in the three dimensions of reading comprehension after using the audio-video presentation?

Table 7. Difference Pretest and Posttest Scores

		Statistic	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Effect Size
Pretest (Multimedia)	Pretest (Conventional)	1176	<0.001	7.00	0.358	1.00

Note: 1 – Wilcoxon W ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

Table 7 presents the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in the three dimensions of reading comprehension after using the audio-video presentation. The data revealed that the respondents’ posttest scores had a significant difference between the pretest scores after the integration of the audio-visual presentation. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there was no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants after using the audio-video presentation, was rejected.

Participants have better posttest scores relative to their pretest scores. This result could be described as indicating that the intervention had contributed to the reading comprehension level of the learners. Thus, the result further implied that utilizing audio-video presentations as a tool to improve reading comprehension skills could aid the different reading comprehension dimensions of the learners. It was recommended for the frequent use of this approach in the learning experiences of the learners.

This was demonstrated by the findings of a study conducted by Asrul et al. (2020), which revealed that the group that received instruction utilizing audio-visual materials outperformed the group that did not get such instruction. It could be said that learners’ reading comprehension was greatly impacted by audio-visual media. The findings of this study indicated that teaching text reading through audiovisual media had greater significance than teaching it through text alone. Because using audiovisual materials to study reading encouraged creativity and relaxation in the learners.

It also improved the oral presentation of an instructor, which was another benefit. Because audio-visual media primarily employs sound and vision rather than text to transmit information, learners might understand the concepts with clarity. It made the students less bored and assisted in getting them to pay attention to the lessons. Sukma (2019), who claimed that videos immersed students in a more contextualized learning environment, backed up the aforementioned assertion. As a result, both the instructor and the students would be able to improve the learning environment in a classroom by utilizing audio-visual materials.

Problem 5: What output can be designed based on the results of the study?

I. Rationale

Reading is one of the essential lifelong skills that a person must learn and be proficient in. Reading can help a person learn new things, gain new knowledge, and identify new opportunities for personal growth. It requires not only recognizing the written text but, most importantly, understanding as nearly as possible how the writer thinks. It involves inferring, predicting, and drawing conclusions from what has been read. This means that the reader must overcome the literal meaning of the written symbols.

Unfortunately, the majority of children struggle to understand what they read, which is a problem that affects education not just in our nation but also globally. Making use of technology, such as audio-video presentations, is one way to address this issue as it currently exists. Thus, the purpose of this action plan is to urge teachers to take into account and specifically address the need to develop or explore alternatives to the conventional approach to help learners become more proficient readers in the current generation.

Moreover, this Action Plan is a collaborative effort involving school administrators and teachers to assist all teachers in developing critical experiences and attaining the necessary skills for academic success and professional growth as well.

I. Objective

The main objective of this action plan is to enhance teachers' knowledge of technology use in order to make audio-visual presentations that would be effectively used in the classroom, especially in enhancing the reading abilities of the learners. Therefore, at the end of the seminar-workshop, teachers are expected to demonstrate their learned skills by producing audio-video presentations that are appropriate for the reading level of their learners.

Date: April 2024

Vision: To increase teachers' proficiency with technology to create audio-visual presentations that will be utilized in the classroom to engage learners, particularly those who struggle with reading.

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Professional Development: Acquiring Technological Skills

<i>Key Action Steps</i>	<i>Persons Responsible</i>	<i>Resources/ Budget Needed</i>	<i>Date of Completion</i>	<i>Threats/ Potential Barriers</i>	<i>Indicators of Success</i>
Conduct seminar-workshop related to ICT				Teachers face difficulties in making the best use of ICT in their instructional practices	Teachers are equipped with the basic skills to make videos.
Invite resource speaker who is expert in making audio-video presentations. (if needed)	Administrators ICT Coordinator Teachers	MOOE Internet Connection Laptop Projector	April 2023	Teachers have inadequate knowledge on ICT related tasks and deficient skills in using ICT software tools and applications	Teachers use audio-video presentations in teaching reading and other subject matter.
ICT Coordinator should provide technical assistance to those teachers who are lacking	ICT Coordinator Teachers	Internet Connection Laptop	End of school year	Teachers lack proficiency with ICT software tools and programs, as well as a lack of understanding about ICT-related tasks.	Teachers are skilled at using both ICT software and video-making applications

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, it was determined that utilizing audio-video presentations could contribute to the learners' reading abilities. It enhanced their comprehension skills in such a way that their senses were much more involved since audio-visual media convey information via sound and image instead of text. In addition, the learners got the ideas clearly, and they were much more participative and motivated when using the audio-video presentation. This is due to the fact that the tools were an interactive approach to teaching reading comprehension, which was appropriate to the current generation. Moreover, the results showed that using audio-video presentations as tools in reading was significant for the learners' retention and comprehension. The results suggested that using technology, such as audio-video presentations, could enhance the teaching process and improve learning outcomes in reading comprehension.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are being offered to be considered. (1) To pique learners'

interest in reading, teachers could try incorporating audio-visual materials into their reading comprehension lessons. Learners remember concepts and information better with the use of audio-visual presentations since it is more interactive and enjoyable for them. (2) To create audio-visual presentations that will be effectively utilized in the classroom, particularly in improving the reading skills of the learners, teachers should attend seminars, workshops, and other pieces of training to enhance their knowledge of how to use technology. (3) To improve the standard of learning in classrooms, school administrators and stakeholders must encourage and support teachers in using audiovisual materials. (4) The proposed action plan may be studied by the school administrators for implementation. (5) Future researchers may explore studies related to interventions, methods and approaches conducive and appropriate to the 21st century learners.

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